

INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP SKILLS AND PERFORMANCE OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL MASTER TEACHERS

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Abstract. The study determined the extent of instructional leadership skills and the extent of performance of public elementary school master teachers. This study employed a non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing descriptive-correlation method. Validated questionnaire and Universal sampling procedure were utilized considering the minimal number of teachers in the research locale. Two hundred fifty (250) public elementary school teachers were the respondents of the study. Using mean, pearson-r, and regression analysis, the findings revealed that the instructional leadership skills were extensive while the extent of performance of public elementary school master teachers was also extensive. Moreover, the overall results disclosed that indicators for the instructional leadership skills were positively correlated to the performance of public elementary school master teachers. Further, results from the regression analysis revealed the following have a strong influence of instructional leadership skills on the performance of public elementary school master teachers: instruction, research, mentoring and coaching, and observation and supervision. It was recommended that the master teachers evaluate and redesign the use of time and school schedules to increase opportunities for professional learning and collaboration, including participation in professional learning communities, peer coaching and observations across classrooms, and collaborative planning. It was also recommended that master teachers regularly conduct needs assessments to identify areas of professional learning most needed and desired by educators.

KEY WORDS

1. Instructional leadership skills.
2. performance of master teachers .
3. mentoring and coaching.

1. Introduction

Master teachers are independent individuals who strive to improve their own learning to deliver effective learning to the learners and their peers. The core component of a master teacher is to deliver high-quality instructional competence to their students and professional development to career teachers. Professional growth is an expectation for the master teacher, not only providing it to others but also searching out opportunities for themselves. Master teachers are highly experienced and skilled educators who have demonstrated exceptional teaching abilities, extensive subject knowledge, and a profound understanding of pedagogical techniques. They often serve as mentors, role models, and leaders within the educational commu-

nity, influencing both students and fellow teachers. Master teachers contribute significantly to the improvement of teaching practices, curriculum development, and overall student learning outcomes. These distinguished educators are typically recognized for their outstanding contributions to the field of education and are often sought after for their insights and guidance. They play a crucial role in shaping the next generation of teachers, sharing their expertise, innovative teaching methods, and practical strategies for creating engaging and effective learning environments. Thus, teacher plays a significant role in the classroom settings or even in the virtual environment so that learners can achieve the desired learning outcomes. As stated in DepEd Memorandum No. 50, Series 2020 also known as the DepEd Professional Development priorities for teachers and school leaders to wit: The professional development priorities shall support the realization of the department's goal of continuous upskilling and reskilling of teachers and school leaders that will result in better learning outcomes. The policy clearly stated that teachers and school leaders need to attend seminars and trainings that could further enhance their capabilities and knowledge on the technological advancement and current trend of our digital society. As competent leaders, they have mastered the management skills of their classrooms and found a way to accelerate learning for all their students. These educators are exceptional communicators who have a strong connection with their students and adapt the curriculum to their learners' needs. They recognize that the education process is about much more than sharing content but creating independent learners who have the critical thinking skills to grow and thrive. Thus, the principle of lifelong learning and the view of the teaching profession as one that requires teachers' expert knowledge and specialized skills, acquired, and maintained through rigorous and continuing study. Globally, master teachers are independent learners who strive to improve their own learning to deliver effective learning to the students and their peers. The core component of a master teacher is to deliver high-quality instructional competence to their students and professional development to career teachers. It may mean that the master teachers foster critical thinking and analytical skills through research and expanding their knowledge and understanding of a chose field outside of the classroom that can be helpful in improving the performance of the learners. The work of educational leaders according to Netolicky (2020) is always complex. It involves strategy, culture, relationships, administration, operations, and complex decision-making, with multiple moving parts and often conflicting stakeholder views. The research evidence also suggests that school leaders do leadership through leading change, entrepreneurialism, partnership building and management, and policy management and implementation (Miller, 2018) According to Celikten (2021), instructional leadership is a broad concept with various definitions describing the roles, actions, and outcomes of instructional leadership. Also, Ozdemir, Sahin, Ozturk (2020) state that instructional leadership is the school leader's practices aimed at achieving success in the teaching-learning process and an effective instructional leader drives all stakeholders towards achieving the school's goals. Similarly, in the Philippines, given the role of master teachers, they should have, revealed by Arcenal (2018), the capability to lead the school particularly in improving the academic performance of the students. In their study, it was found out that master teachers' instructional leadership capacity showed "Highly Proficient" especially on curriculum content and pedagogy, on planning, assessing, and reporting learners' outcomes and on personal growth and professional development. In the study of Clariño (2020) also echoed in his study on Organizational Support, Instructional and Professional Competencies of Master

Teachers: A theory that master teachers possess an advanced level of instructional competence in terms of content, knowledge, and pedagogy, learning environment, diversity of learners, curriculum, and planning and in assessment and reporting. In contrast, Romero (2019) identified that one of master teachers' problems is lack of required skills and competence in conducting instructional supervision. Hence, Clariño (2020) recommended that master teachers should always sustain their levels of instructional and professional competence through attendance in graduate school programs, participation in workshops and conferences as well as engagement in various training. In the study of Golingay (2018) it stated that Instructional competence is rooted from the colossal attributes possessed by the teachers, which embraces the potential abilities, skills, knowledge, personal character, experiences, and others that necessitate in their teaching professions. In the study of Martel as cited in Nair (2017) discussed that competen-

cies play a primary role in the creation of a culture of ongoing learning. This makes it possible to achieve their goals and continue improving their competencies and learning throughout life. For teachers, the recognition of acquired competencies makes it possible to move forward in their training and continue progressing in their professional development. In Maa District, it implies that master teacher's instructional competence is essential and significant tools needed for teaching and learning to promote teacher's efficiency and improve learner's performance. For teachers, the recognition of acquired competencies makes it possible to move forward in their training and continue progressing in their professional development. that teachers' competence, knowledge interest, devotion, commitment, dedication, professional training, attitude, and personality make up matters and largely determine the quality of services provided by the teacher.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research methods, which give direction in this investigation. It includes the research design, research respondents of the study, research instrument and the data gathering procedures.

2.1. Research Design—This study used the non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing correlational method. According to Magsayo (2021), descriptive correlational method is used to determine the relationship between two or more variables and to ascertain their relationship. More to the point, Palayon (2019) emphasizes that this method is used since the study provides a description of individuals and aims to explain the nature of the data. This study is descriptive in nature since it assesses instructional leadership skills and performance of public elementary school master teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City. This is correlational since it determines instructional

leadership skills and performance of public elementary school master teachers.

2.2. Research Respondents—This study was conducted in seven (7) schools of Maa District, Division of Davao City. The respondents were composed of 120-selected teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City. They have been in the service for at least five to ten years teaching experiences in the Department of Education (DepED) and have said something on the instructional leadership skills and performance of public elementary school master teachers. Random sampling technique was employed in this study. However, Langub Elementary School and Magtuod Elementary School with

100 percent of respondents were involved. For the rest of the schools, fifty percent were given the questionnaires. The schools are equidistantly located in the whole district, which can be reached by means of land transportation facilities. The environment is conducive to educational research.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This study adapted a questionnaire on school environment which was patterned and adapted by the researcher from instructional leadership skills by Hallinger and Murphy (1985) as cited by Magsayo (2017). This theory deals with school environment that shaped teachers and learners’ experiences. It was characterized by supportive leadership, teacher collaboration, high expectations for learners, and a collective commitment to support learning. This is supported by Bacon’s (2001) theory of performance of teachers as cited by Bacullo (2021). Teachers were motivated to be at their highest levels of effort and participation, maintained optimistic attitudes and thereby generated greater efficiency and work performance. Teacher performance evaluation plays a key role in educational personnel reform, so it has been an important yet difficult issue in educational reform. The questionnaire was modified mainly through the researcher’s preferences to suit the needs of the study. The adapted questionnaire was vali-

dated by the experts from the DepEd-Division of Davao City. Validity of the instrument was ensured through expert’s opinions and pilot testing. To ensure the reliability of the instrument, a pilot test was conducted through calculating the value of Cronbach’s Alpha with the obtained values of 0.694. The questionnaire was divided into two (2) parts, instructional leadership skills and performance of public elementary school master teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City. Hence, the Cronbach’s value of the construct has met the minimum reliability of 0.684, it means that the measures used were consistent enough for the study. In terms of instrument’s face validity, the items were modified to suit the purpose of this study and were validated by experts. The questionnaire was presented to the adviser for comments, corrections, and suggestions. Part 1 of the questionnaire contained the items on instructional leadership skills with the following aspects instruction, research, mentoring and coaching and observation and supervision. Part 2 pertained to the performance of master teachers with the dimensions, namely: curriculum content and pedagogy, planning assessment and reporting, and personal growth and professional development. The perceptions of the respondents among the Maa District teachers were based on the following Five-point Likert rating scales:

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very Extensive	The instructional leadership skills are always evident.
3.40-4.19	Extensive	The instructional leadership skills are often-times evident.
2.60-3.39	Moderately Extensive	The instructional leadership skills are some-times evident.
1.80-2.59	Less Extensive	The instructional leadership skills are rarely evident.
1.00-1.79	Not Extensive	The instructional leadership skills are not evident.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very Extensive	The performance of master teachers' is always evident.
3.40-4.19	Extensive	The performance of master teachers' is oftentimes evident.
2.60-3.39	Moderately Extensive	The performance of master teachers' is sometimes evident.
1.80-2.59	Less Extensive	The performance of master teachers' is rarely evident.
1.00-1.79	Not Extensive	The performance of master teachers' is not evident.

1. Permission to Conduct Study. The researcher wrote a letter asking permission from the Dean of Graduate School to conduct this research study. The researcher secured a permit to conduct the study from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Davao City through channels to the Office of the Public Schools District Supervisor (PSDS) of the different schools. 2. Distribution and retrieval of questionnaires. Upon approval of the permit to conduct the study, the sets of questionnaires were sent to the respondents via google forms and through email-add of the school heads and teachers. The questionnaires were retrieved right after the respondents were through answering the questions and sent them back through researcher's email-add or messenger. 3. Collection and statistical treatment of data. The data were collected during

the Corona Virus Pandemic (COVID-19) time; therefore, the collection of data was based on the protocols set by the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) standards. It is a task force organized by the executive of the Philippine government to respond to affairs concerning emerging infectious diseases in the Philippine which was convened in January 2023. The collection of data was conducted following the protocols of IATF to avoid being contaminated and infected by COVID-19. For some participants who missed answering the questionnaire, the video call, via messenger, viber, zoom or goggle meet were used to gather the data or responses of the participants. These were submitted to the statistician for analysis. The researcher together with the statistician tabulated the data, analyzed, and subject them for statistical analysis.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools were used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in this study: Mean. It was used to determine the extent of instructional leadership skills and performance of public elementary school master teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson-r). This statistical tool was used in determining the sig-

nificant components of instructional leadership skills and performance of public elementary school master teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City. Multiple Linear Regression. This was used to utilize to determine the significant influence of components of instructional leadership skills and performance of public elementary school master teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City.

3. Results and Discussion

Presented in this chapter were the results of the data gathered. Two sets of research were employed to determine the extent of instructional leadership skills and performance of public elementary school master teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City. The discussion of the results and interpretations were presented accordingly based on the statement of the problems. Presentation of the interpretation was arranged according to the sub-headings: The extent of instructional leadership skills in terms of instruction, research, mentoring and coaching, and observation and supervision; the extent of performance of public elementary school master teachers in terms of curriculum content and pedagogy, planning assessment and reporting, and personal growth and professional development; and which of the factors of instructional leadership skills significantly influence the performance of public elementary school master teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City.

Summary on the Extent of Instructional Leadership Skills. Presented in table 1 shows the summary on the extent of instructional leadership skills of public elementary school master teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City. The indicator with highest mean is instruction with a mean of (3.99), interpreted as extensive. Then, it is followed by observation and supervision has a mean of (3.83) identified as high. Furthermore, research has gained a mean of (3.67) or extensive. Lastly, mentoring and coaching has the least mean of (3.57) described as extensive. With an overall generated mean of (3.76) or extensive, therefore the summary extent of instructional leadership skills was extensive as perceived by public elementary school master teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City.

Table 1. Summary on the Extent of Instructional Leadership Skills

No	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Instruction	3.99	Extensive
2	Research	3.67	Extensive
3	Mentoring and Coaching	3.57	Extensive
4	Observation and Supervision	3.84	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.76	Extensive

It can be gleaned from the table that instruction, observation and supervision, research, and mentoring and coaching were extensive. Mentoring and coaching were the least among the indicators of instructional leadership skills of public elementary school master teachers. Therefore, Mentoring and coaching seem to have taken over many other forms of job embedded professional development programs across the globe. Mentoring involves providing professional and personal guidance to an assigned mentee. Coaching involves providing focused career assistance to a coach. This finding is complementary to the idea of Rajagani (2014), that mentoring and coaching are not the same but have similar attributes. Mentoring involves helping mentees (teachers) in areas of professional (career, skills, and expertise) and per-

sonal (work/life balance, self-confidence, self-perception, personal influences) by building relationship. Mentors in general are much more experienced and are able to share with their mentee (beginner teacher) about school policies,

rules, school culture, protocols; teaching methods and related issues, provide personal and professional support; and guide the new teacher through reflection and professional discussions.

Summary on the Extent of Performance of Public Elementary School Masters. Presented in table 2 shows the summary on the extent of performance of public elementary school master teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City. The indicator with highest mean is curriculum and pedagogy with a mean of (4.02), interpreted as extensive. Then, it is followed by personal growth and professional development

has a mean of (3.91) which also identified as extensive. Lastly, planning assessment and reporting has the least mean of (3.86) described as extensive. With an overall generated mean of (3.93) or extensive, therefore the summary on the extent of performance of public elementary school was extensive as perceived by the master teachers.

Table 2. Summary on the Extent of Performance of Public Elementary School Masters Teachers

No	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Curriculum and Pedagogy	4.02	Extensive
2	Planning Assessment and Reporting	3.86	Extensive
3	Personal Growth and Professional Development	3.91	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.93	Extensive

It can be gathered from the table that planning assessment and reporting, and personal growth and professional development were extensive. The planning assessment and reporting was the least among the indicators of performance of public elementary school master teachers. Continuing Professional Development (CPD) improves teachers' professional knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values. In the Philippines, the government promulgated the CPD Act of 2016 to step up the country's community following international standards. The law mandates that professionals earn required CPD units through participation in seminars, training, and other programs as a requirement for the Philippine Regulation Commission (PRC) license renewal. PRC is an agency that regulates laws and policies for different regulated profes-

sions and issues licenses for professionals like teachers. Teachers' CPD has become one of the most common central concerns in educational studies over several decades. The professional development of teachers is the most significant way to affect their quality of teaching. CPD provides the teachers with new content knowledge, pedagogical skills, and innovations to improve teaching and learn in different contexts. It also promotes the collaboration of best practices of teachers and other experts in education from various institutions. Relationship Between the Instructional Leadership Skills and Performance Master of Public Elementary School Master Teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City Shown in Table 3 is the statistical analysis on the significant relationship between the of instructional leadership skills and performance

of public elementary school master teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City. Based on the analysis, the overall p-value is equal to 0.000 with an r-value equal to 0.883. This means that there is a very strong positive significant association between the extent of instructional leadership skills and the extent of performance of public elementary school master teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City. Hence, this study rejects its established null hypothesis. The analysis further implies if there is an increase in the level of instructional leadership skills, this will lead also to an increase of performance of public elementary school master teachers of Maa District, Divi-

sion of Davao City. Effective teaching is the prime duty of a professional teacher. Changes in the teaching profession are without end due to the nature of the profession, which is ever-changing timelessly. The teacher is the most significant agent in the teaching-learning process. Teachers could either make or unmake the future of students. Professional development can be enhanced through faculty development activities such as instructional planning, instructional delivery, knowledge of the subject matter, rapport with the students and classroom management. There is a rise in teaching strategies in the twenty-first century through teamwork and innovation (Nairz-Wirth Feldmann, 2019).

Table 3. Relationship Between the Instructional Leadership Skills and Performance Mastery of Public Elementary School Master Teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City

Instructional Leadership Skills	Performance of Master Teachers	r	p-value	Decision on H0	Interpretation
Instruction		0.688	0.000	Reject	There is a strong positive significant correlation
Research		0.565	0.000	Reject	There is a moderate positive significant correlation
Mentoring and Coaching		0.445	0.000	Reject	There is a moderate positive significant correlation
Observation and Supervision		0.673	0.000	Reject	There is a strong positive significant correlation
Overall		0.801	0.000	Reject	There is a very strong positive significant correlation

Specifically, the said analysis highlighted the specific relationship between each factor of instructional leadership skills and performance of public elementary school master teachers of Maa District. Based on the analysis depicted in said table, the Instruction factor of instructional leadership skills of public elementary school master teachers of Maa District ranked as the top indicator with a p-value of 0.000 and r-value of 0.688. This result implies that there is a strong positive significant relationship between the instruction as factor of instructional leadership skills and performance of public elementary school master teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City. This was followed by the Observation and Supervision factor of instructional leadership skills of public elementary school master teachers of Maa District obtaining a p-value of 0.000 and r -value of 0.673.

Still, this means that there is a strong positive significant relationship between the observation and supervision as factor of instructional leadership skills and performance of public elementary school master teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City. The third one is the Research factor which obtained a p-value of 0.000 and r -value of 0.565. This means that there is a moderate positive significant relationship between the research as factor of instructional leadership skills and performance of public elementary school master teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City. Lastly, the Mentoring and Coaching factor of instructional leadership skills obtained a p-value of 0.000 and r -value of 0.445. This means that there is a moderate positive significant relationship between the mentoring and coaching skills of the instructional leadership skills and performance of pub-

lic elementary school master teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City.

Regression Analysis on the Significant Influence of the Instructional Leadership Skills on the Performance of Public Elementary School Master Teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City

As shown in table 4, the overall regression analysis obtained p-value of less 0.000 and F-value equal to 59.818 stating that the instructional leadership skills has a significant influence on the performance of public elementary school master teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City. This also implies that the regression model used in the analysis of the study is useful and that there is validity in the interpretation on the assumption of the said influences. Relatively, the regression analysis as presented in the same table shows all the factors under

fluence the performance of public elementary school master teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City. Hence, the set null hypothesis of this study that there are no factors of instructional leadership skills that significantly influence the performance of public elementary school master teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City is rejected. Specifically, these factors under the instructional leadership skills of master’s teachers in accordance to their t-value are the Instruction factor which obtained a t-value equal to 7.049 and a p-value equal to 0.000, the Observation and Supervision factor which obtained a t-value equal to 5.163 and a p-value equal to 0.000, the Mentoring and Coaching factor which obtained a t-value equal to 2.708 and a p-value less than 0.008, and the last is the Research factor which obtained a t-value equal to 2.258 and a p-value less than 0.040.

Table 4. Regression Analysis on the Significant Influence of the Instructional Leadership Skills on the Performance of Public Elementary School Master Teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City

Performance of Master Teachers Instructional Leadership Skills	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients				
	β	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Decision on Ho
Constant	.639	.228		2.802	.006	
Instruction	.334	.047	.435	7.049	.000	Reject
Research	.103	.056	.126	2.258	.040	Reject
Mentoring and Coaching	.155	.057	.163	2.708	.008	Reject
Observation and Supervision	.266	.051	.345	5.163	.000	Reject

R = 0.822, R² = 0.675, F-Value = 59.818, p-value < .000

Moreover, the established results of the regression analysis garnered an R2 equal to 0.675. This means that there are 67.5 percent ascribed to the significance influence of instructional leadership skills that significantly influenced performance of public elementary school master teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City. This 67.5 percent variation in the performance of master teachers is accounted for by instructional leadership skills, which implies that these skills are a major factor affecting performance according to the regression analysis.

Thus, the other 32.5 percent is ascribed to the other indicators not stipulated in the study. Particularly, these indicators could be included to determine that they might have stipulated influence on the performance of public elementary school master teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City. In addition, the 32.5 percent "unexplained" variance indicates a need for further research to identify additional factors that could be affecting performance of public elementary school master teachers. This also suggests that while instructional leadership skills are signifi-

cant, they are not the only factors at play.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This section presents the findings of the study based on the data outcome. The conclusions drawn from the findings of the study are likewise outlined in this section. To maximize the significant contribution of this study, the researcher has laid down recommendations in this chapter.

4.1. Findings—This non-experimental research using correlation design in this study aimed to determine the extent of instructional leadership skills and performance of public elementary school master teachers. Specifically, this study aimed to determine the extent of instructional leadership skills in terms of instruction, research, mentoring and coaching, and observation and supervision. Moreover, this identified the extent of performance of public elementary school master teachers in terms of curriculum content and pedagogy, planning assessment and reporting, and personal growth and professional development. Finally, this study determined the significant relationship between the extent of instructional leadership skills and the extent of performance of public elementary school master teachers. Using non-experimental research, the extent of instructional leadership skills and performance of public elementary school master teachers was determined. The respondents of the study were the 120-public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City. A modified teacher-made survey questionnaire was adopted from the study of Maslow's Need Theory (1943) as cited by Gibertas (2015) and Bridging Theory and Practice as cited by Graham (2022) was utilized as the main instrument of this study. After thorough analysis, significant findings showed that the extent of instructional management skills in terms of instruction, research, mentoring and coaching, and observation and supervision was extensive. Similarly, the extent of performance of public elementary school master teachers in terms of curriculum content

and pedagogy, planning assessment and reporting, and personal growth and professional development was also extensive which means that it was sometimes manifested while in terms of instructional leadership skills which also extensive. Hence, the extent of instructional leadership skills as demonstrated by public elementary school master teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City was extensive. Finally, indicators of instructional leadership skills such as instruction, observation and supervision, coaching, and research have significant influence on performance of public elementary school master teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were offered: The extent of instructional leadership skills of public elementary school master teachers was extensive. The extent of performance of public elementary school master teachers was also extensive. There was a strong positive correlation between instructional leadership skills and performance of public elementary school master teachers based on the indicators. Based on the results revealed, the following indicators have a strong influence of instructional leadership skills on the performance of public elementary school master teachers: Instruction, Observation and Supervision, Coaching, and Research.

4.3. Recommendations—The following interventions were offered based on the conclusions of the study: School Heads may send their master teachers to attend seminars/ trainings to abreast themselves with the latest develop-

ment in education and engage themselves in any professional activities that will uplift their instructional competence and instructional leadership capacity. Adopt standards for professional development and instructional competencies to guide the design, evaluation, and funding of professional learning provided to educators. These standards might reflect the features of effective professional learning outlined in this report as well as standards for implementation. Evaluate and redesign the use of time and school schedules to increase opportunities for professional learning and collaboration, including participation in professional learning communities, peer coaching and observations across classrooms, and collaborative planning. Regularly conduct needs assessments using data from staff surveys to identify areas of professional learning most needed and desired by educators. Data from these sources can help ensure that professional learning is not disconnected from practice and supports the areas of knowledge and skills educators want to develop. Future Researchers may use the findings of this as springboard to conduct a study with a similar subject but with a larger scope to explore other dimensions of the study.

5. References

- Arce, N. (2019). Mentoring as a collaborative learning journey for teachers and student teachers: A critical constructivist perspective, *Teacher Education Advancement Network Journal*, University of Cambria, Vol. 6, pp, 17-27
- Arcenal, H. (2018), Foreign language teaching assistant professional development: Challenges and strategies in meeting the 2007 MLA report's calls for change. In J. Swaffar & P. Urlaub (Eds.), *Transforming postsecondary foreign language teaching in the United States* (pp. 177-191). New York: NY, Springer.
- Badri, M. (2016). Perception of teachers' professional development needs, impacts, and barriers: The Abu Dhabi case. *Sage Journals*
- Bueno, D.C. (2019). Research skills and attitudes of master teachers in a division towards capability training. *Philippine International Conference on Economics, Education, Humanities & Social Sciences*
- Bukoye, R.O. (2018). Utilization of instruction materials as tools for effective academic performance of students: Implications for counseling. *Innovative and Creative Education and Teaching International Conference*
- Celikten, J. (2021). Differentiation: Lessons from master teachers: Improving instruction for students with learning needs. *Educational leadership* 64(5): 44 – 47.
- Clariño, M. (2020), Language resources in repositories and catalogues: Pilot study on their potential for LSP teaching and training *BOOK google.com*.
- Darling-Hammond, (2017). Evaluating teacher evaluation. *Phi Delta Kappan*, 93(6), 8-15. doi:10.1177/003172171209300603.
- Gabriel, S. (2015). Teaching leaders to lead teachers: educational administration. in the era of constant crisis. *Advances in Educational Administration*, Volume 10. page 126.
- Gleason, A. & Gerzon, (2018). The bricks and mortar of our foundation for faculty development: Book-study within a self-study professional learning.
- Golingay, G. (2018). Instructional Competence of Grade Eleven Teachers and Academic Performance of Students: Basis for Proposed Training Program <http://x.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3789579>

- Hart (2019). Strategies for culturally and linguistically diverse students with special needs. *Preventing School Failure*, 53, 197-208. doi:10.3200/PSFL.53.3.197-208
- Hirsh, S. (2019). A new definition. *Theme/Learning Schools*. National Staff Development Council, Vol. 30, No.
- Huizing, L. (2018). Mentoring together: A literature review of group mentoring, mentoring, and tutoring: *Partnership in learning*, 20:1, 27-55, DOI:10.1080/13611267.2012.645599
- Ikromova, A., (2020). The concept of pedagogical skills, its role and importance in teaching. *The American Journal of Applied Sciences*, doi:10.37547/tajas, Volume 2, Issue 8 – 17.
- Ivior, M. G. (2014). The Meaning and Importance of Curriculum Development. <http://simplyeducate.me/2014/12/13/the-meaning-and-importance-of-curriculum-development>
- Laude, et. al. (2018). Master teachers as instructional leaders: An exploration of school leadership capacity in the Division of Biliran, *International Journal of Sciences: Basic and Applied Research (IJSBAR)*, Volume 40, No. 1, pp. 50-74.
- Marey, R. (2020). Re-conceptualizing teacher evaluation and supervision in the light of educational reforms in Egypt. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 2(1).
- Miller, A. (2018). Investigating the impacts of targeted professional development around models and modeling on teachers' instructional practice and student learning <https://doi.org/10.1002/tea.21434>
- McClellan, W. (2019)/The master teacher: Role and responsibilities in the reform process. www.eric.ed.gov.
- Meador, D. (2017). Effective Strategies to Increase Parental Involvement in Education <https://www.thoughtco.com/increase-parental-involvement-in-education-3194407>. February 17, 2017
- Mohana, P. and Enoch, A. (2017). Mentoring for career development – a strategic approach for employee retention abstract. *MIM International Journal of Management Research*. Vol – 3, ISSN 2394 – 6997.
- Moore, A. (2015). Master teachers as instructional leaders: An instrumental case study. *Liberty University ProQuest Dissertations Publishing*, 2015.3712713.

- Mwakapina, V. E. (2016). The Key Elements of a Successful School-Based Management Strategy. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 14 (3), 351-372.
- Netolicky, D. (2020). Transformational professional learning: What, why and how? *Independent Education* 50(1), 3 <https://search.informit.org/doi/10.3316/informit.085245862139>.
- Petrovska, S. et al. (2018). Mentoring in teaching profession. *International Journal Aof Cognitive Research in Science, Engineering and Education*, Vol. 6, Issue 2. DOI:10.5937/ijcrsee1802047P.
- Richter, D. et al. (2018). Professional development across the teaching career: Teachers' uptake of formal and informal learning opportunities. *Teaching and Teacher education*, 27(1) 116 – 126. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2010.07.008
- Romero, M. et., al. (2019). Master teacher as teacher leaders: Evidence from Malaysia and the Philippines. *ISEA*. Volume 42, Number.
- Salgur, A.S., (2019). Importance of mentoring in teacher training. *Lumira Southeast Europe University*, Vol.5 No.2, p.48.
- Sangalang, L. A. (2018). Mentoring skills and technical assistance of master teachers in Pangasinan. *PSU Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, psurj.org
- Tomlinson, C. A. (2018). *The Differentiated Classroom: Responding to the Needs of all Learners*. Alexandria: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development
- Wong, J. (2020). Teaching Competence and Attitude Towards the Teaching Profession of Senior High School Teachers: Education Vs. Non-Education. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education, Arts and Sciences*, 7(1), 54-61.
- Ying, G. (2018). Linking mentor teachers' motivations to their mentoring conceptions, Teacher, and Teaching: theory and practice, DOI: 10.1080/13540602.2015.1023031.